

Constraining the Black Hole Spin of Arakelian 120

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Abstract

A ~ 100 ks *Suzaku* observation (4 April 2007) of the Arakelian 120 (Ark 120) bare Seyfert 1 galaxy produces an X-ray spectrum with features from a soft excess, hard excess, and extended structure in the iron line band (Nardini et al. 2011). We compare this to the previously examined (Patrick et al. 2011) ~ 112 ks *XMM-Newton* observation (24 August 2003). We model the spectrum by first building a phenomenological model using blackbody, Gaussian, and accretion disk components with and without relativistic effects convolved. Then, we allow a black hole spin parameter to vary freely within a self-consistent physical model that assumes all three excess features result from the same Comptonization process. As bare Seyferts lack substantial volumes of photoionized gas near their central regions, the possibility of absorption features masking the intrinsic properties of our spectral continuum is remote. With the advantage of multi-epoch and multi-instrument data, we make constrain the spin of the supermassive black hole at the center of Ark 120 to be $0.94^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$.

Section 1: Introduction

Most galaxies are thought to host a supermassive black hole (SMBH), which can be exclusively described by mass and by black hole (BH) spin. The dimensionless BH spin parameter is proportional to angular momentum (Figure 1). Constraints on a galaxy's BH spin parameter can provide key information on the kinematics, the morphology, and the evolution of the host galaxy. That is, such constraints are crucial for determining the direction of BH spin and for determining whether perturbations in the accretion disk cause relativistic outflows (Lohfink et al. 2011). The spin of a black hole is also closely related to the arrangement of its host galaxy, e.g. elliptical galaxies are thought to have on average higher spin parameters than disk galaxies (Volonteri et al. 2007). Finally, the observed distribution of BH spin parameters reveal information about a black hole's past interactions with its environment. For example, the lifetimes of quasars provide enough time for the innermost regions of the accretion disk to align with BH spin values (Volonteri et al. 2005). Better telescope collecting area and spectral resolution have accelerated progress in constraining BH spin in the past decade (Brenneman & Reynolds, 2006).

$$a = \frac{cJ}{GM^2}$$

Figure 1 – This equation defines the BH spin parameter, which is measured per unit mass. For a prograde BH, the spin parameter theoretically varies between 0 for a non-rotating BH and 1 for a maximally spinning BH. In reality, the spin parameter is limited to 0.998 because a rapidly spinning black hole prefers to accrete photons with negative angular momentum (Thorne 1974).

The relativistic accretion of gas onto a SMBH is thought to produce the large luminosities associated with active galactic nuclei (AGN) (Salpeter 1964). The X-ray spectrum of AGN is composed of a power law continuum and a reflection spectrum, both of which originate from physical processes. First, the accretion disk emits ultraviolet photons, which are inverse Compton scattered into X-rays by high-energy electrons in the corona (Figure 2). Each scattering becoming more unlikely, causing more flux at lower energies and less at higher energies; this produces an inverse power law (Rybicki & Lightman 1979). Then, some of these X-ray continuum photons are reflected back onto neutral absorbing material (Figure 3) and onto the

inner accretion disk. A metal can absorb the X-ray if its energy exceeds the threshold energy for a certain photoelectric transition (Reynolds 2003), producing a reflection spectrum of fluorescent lines (Figure 4). In particular, the iron line juts prominently above the power-law continuum because of its abundance, high energy, and high fluorescent yield. Information about BH spin lies in the shape of the broad iron $K\alpha$ fluorescent line (Figure 5), because relativistic effects arising from BH spin can broaden the intrinsically narrow iron line.

Figure 2 – This figure (Reynolds 2003) shows that the inner regions of AGN is thought to be composed of a supermassive black hole (black dot), an accretion disk (red line), and a corona (yellow) of unknown geometry. The red arrow represents the emission of ultraviolet photons from the accretion disk. The blue arrow represents the scattering of such photons off of high-energy electrons in the corona.

Figure 3 – This figure (Reynolds 2003) shows a neutral absorbing medium (blue) on the order of 10-100 thousand gravitational radii away from the supermassive black hole and accretion disk. Jets (yellow) may flow from the center of a galaxy of a radio-loud source.

Figure 4 – This figure (Reynolds & Nowak 2003) shows a reflection spectrum alongside a power law continuum. The inverse power law typically has a slope of negative 2 for AGN, when plotted in log-log space. The iron (Fe) line peaks above the power law. Other fluorescent emission lines (Ne, Mg, etc) at lower energies are present but dominated by the power law.

Figure 5 – This figure (Laura Brenneman, private communication) shows an example spectrum (black) from a static disk. In contrast, the spectrum of photons reflected off of a relativistic accretion disk (red) is distorted, broadened, and smeared by relativistic effects.

In this paper, we examine the X-ray spectrum of the source Arakelian 120 (Ark 120), a type 1 bare Seyfert AGN (1.86×10^8 solar masses, $z = 0.0327$). As bare Seyferts lack substantial volumes of photoionized gas near their central regions, the possibility of absorption features masking the intrinsic properties of our spectral continuum is remote. The radio-quiet classification of Ark 120 further facilitates a clean view of the regions close to the black hole. An unobscured survey of the inner regions of the AGN will assist the examination of the relationship between the iron $K\alpha$ emission and the relativistic reflection off of the inner accretion disk.

Our analysis furthers previous research (Patrick et al. 2011) that used data spanning different epochs to constrain the spin of the black hole at the center of Ark 120. However, Patrick et al. did not analyze Ark 120 *XMM* data in conjunction with *Suzaku* data, as we do in this paper. We add the *XMM* data to give us even higher signal-to-noise ratio for the overlapping energy ranges of the X-ray spectrum. Our analysis also furthers previous research (Nardini et al. 2011) that used *Suzaku* data to perform spectral analysis on Ark 120. However, Nardini et al. did not pursue a robust spin constraint of the BH spin, giving a preliminary estimate of the spin without a formal error analysis. We employ a self-consistent physical approach, in addition to building up a model component-by-component like the phenomenological approach of Nardini et al. 2011.

We organize our work in the following fashion. Section 2 discusses observation and data reduction. Section 3 presents the analysis and results. Section 4 presents the discussion of results. Section 5 summarizes the paper and suggests areas of future research.

Section 2: Observation and Data Reduction

Section 2.1: Observations

This paper uses a ~ 100 ks *Suzaku* observation from the X-ray imaging spectrometer (XIS) and an accompanying ~ 89 ks *Suzaku* observation (4 April 2007) from the HXD/PIN detector, obtained

from public HEASARC¹ archives. We accessed event files from XIS CCDs in 3x3 (71ks exposure) as well as 5x5 (30ks exposure) modes. The XIS0 and XIS3 are both front-illuminated (FI) chips, whereas the XIS1 is a back-illuminated detector. For this paper, we co-added data from the front-illuminated CCDs and excluded our analysis of the back-illuminated data, to take advantage of the higher signal-to-noise offered by FI data and for simplicity in plotting. XIS2, the other FI detector, has not been operational since November 2006. We then use the PIN instrument of the *Suzaku* HXD to extend our available energy range from 10 keV to 40 keV.

This paper also uses a ~112ks *XMM-Newton* observation (24 August 2003) obtained from public HEASARC² archives. The *XMM* has the largest collecting area of any X-ray observatory, offering a high signal-to-noise ratio. We use the *XMM* EPIC-pn detector, whose well-calibrated energy range spans 0.5-10 keV, over the EPIC MOS instrument to maximize our collecting area and signal-to-noise. While the *XMM* also has a grating spectrometer that attains high resolving power over the range of 0.33-2.5 keV, analysis of high spectral resolution of Ark 120 at lower energies is beyond the scope of this paper.

Section 2.2: Data Reduction

For the reduction of *Suzaku* XIS data, we followed the instructions in the *Suzaku* Data Reduction Guide³. First, we used the HEASoft reduction and analysis package (version 6.8) to duplicate the *Suzaku* processing pipeline (calibration and re-screening). From these event files, we used XSELECT to extract source spectra and light curves using an extraction radius of 250 pixels. We also extracted background spectra from adjacent regions uncontaminated by the source. Then, we made redistribution matrix files (rmf) using the ‘xismrfgen’ script and ancillary response files (arf) using the ‘xissimarfgen’ script. Finally, the source spectra, background spectra, and response files for the front-illuminated XIS0 and XIS3 chips were combined and rebinned by a factor of 8 (from 4096 original spectral channels to 512 bins). This was a suitable factor change to compress the spectra without compromising the spectral resolution of the data.

For the reduction of the *Suzaku* PIN data, we first used the ‘hxdpinxbpi’ script to correct the background spectrum by a factor of ten for oversampling (i.e. background files were scaled up by a factor of ten to suppress Poisson noise)⁴. Then, we corrected for dead time (the time after each event during which the system is not able to record another event) using the script ‘hxddtcor’. Additionally, because the HXD is not an imaging instrument, we used a simulated event file to account for non X-ray background (NXB). We also adjusted for the cosmic X-ray (CXB) background, which accounts for about 5%⁵ of the background.

For the reduction of the *XMM* data, we followed the instructions in the *XMM-Newton ABC Guide*⁶. First, we used the Science Analysis Software⁷ to run the calibration using the ‘cifbuild’ and ‘odfingest’ scripts and to duplicate the processing pipeline using the ‘epchain’ command.

¹ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/W3Browse/>

² <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/W3Browse/>

³ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/suzaku/analysis/abc/>

⁴ ftp://legacy.gsfc.nasa.gov/suzaku/doc/general/suzaku_abc_guide.pdf

⁵ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/suzaku/analysis/abc/node10.html>

⁶ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/xmm/abc/abc.html>

⁷ <http://xmm.esac.esa.int/sas/>

We used the ‘xmmselect’ tool to create and display a light curve, to apply temporal and spatial filters, and to extract source and background spectra. Then, we made redistribution matrix files (rmf) using the ‘rmfgen’ script and ancillary response files (arf) using the ‘arfgen’ script; these files were combined.

To obtain sufficient counts (≥ 25) per spectral channel for the use of the chi-squared statistic when modeling the data, we restricted our analysis to energies within 0.5-10 keV for the *XMM* EPIC-pn instrument, 0.7-10 keV for the *Suzaku* XIS-FI detectors (excluding the 1.5-2.0 keV range, in which there are uncalibrated silicon features), and 14.0-40.0 keV for the *Suzaku* HXD/PIN detector.

The different count rates for the instruments reflect differences in the effective areas of the telescopes as well as differences in flux of the source between the two observations. The count rate for the *Suzaku* XIS-FI instrument is $1.748 \pm 2.973 \times 10^{-3}$ (98.8% of 1.769 total counts) with an exposure time of 202ks. The count rate for the *Suzaku* PIN instrument is $0.122 \pm 4.340 \times 10^{-3}$ (18.7% of 0.652 total counts) with an exposure time of 89.5ks. Finally, the count rate for the *XMM* EPIC-PN instrument is $27.65 \pm 1.886 \times 10^{-2}$ (99.6% of 27.76 total counts) with an exposure time of 78.2ks.

There is some small-amplitude X-ray variability on the short time scale of the observation. Figure 6 shows the light curves for XIS0, XIS1, XIS3, and PIN data. We notice that the flux rises and then falls; the count rate changes at most by 36.8% during the observation. Figure 7 shows the light curve for the *XMM* data. The flux rises and then plateaus; the count rate changes by at most by 11.2% during the observation. The small variation in flux in both of these observations renders our time-averaged flux a valid representation of the X-ray emission from Ark 120.

Figure 6 - These are the background-subtracted light curves of Ark 120 for the operational *Suzaku* XIS detectors. The gentle variation makes our time-averaged flux value a valid representation of the X-ray emission from Ark 120.

Figure 7 – This is the background-subtracted light curve of Ark 120 for the *XMM-Newton* EPIC-pn detector.

Section 3: Analysis

An X-ray spectrum can be parameterized by variables that characterize the properties of the system of the source (like BH spin or iron abundance). We used the X-Ray Spectral Fitting Package (XSPEC) version 12.7.1 to build a phenomenological model for our data, as well as to construct a physically self-consistent model for our data. Starting with phenomenological values helped us to pick appropriate starting parameter values for the physical model.

The modeling technique used in this paper is the chi-square minimization. In all ensuing tables, we present the chi-squared factor per degrees of freedom in the model, which represents the deviation between the model and data (normalized by the number of degrees of freedom).

In both ensuing models, we froze the inclination of the system at 55° , which is in between 57^{+5}_{-12} (Nardini et al. 2011) and 48^{+3}_{-6} (Patrick et al. 2011).

Section 3.1: Phenomenological Analysis

We observed an excess of flux above the power law in the soft energy ranges, in the hard energy ranges, and near the iron $K\alpha$ line. To address each of these three excesses, we first took a phenomenological approach by fitting each excess with a different model component.

Section 3.1.1: Fitting the Power Law

When fitted with a power law, the *Suzaku* data and *XMM* data produce an X-ray spectrum with features from a soft excess, a hard excess (Compton hump), and an extended structure in the iron line band (Nardini et al. 2011). Figure 8 shows the data to model ratio plot obtained from fitting the *Suzaku* and *XMM* X-ray spectra with a basic power law model over the 2-4.5 and 4.5-10 keV

energy ranges, which is consistent with the phenomenological approach. We note that analyzing the *XMM* data jointly with the *Suzaku* extends our maximum energy from 10 keV to 40 keV. It also increases the signal-to-noise ratio where the soft excess (<2 keV) and iron line structure exist (4.5-7.2 keV).

Figure 8 – The *Suzaku* XIS0+XIS3 (black) and PIN (red) and *XMM* (green) spectra of Ark 120 plotted alongside data to model ratio plots after fitting the 2.0–4.5 keV and 7.2–10.0 keV ranges with a power law. The straight green line corresponds to a theoretical perfect fit, with a data to model ratio of one. This plot clearly brings out the smooth soft excess below 2 keV, a prominent iron line feature around 6 keV, and a hard excess beyond 10 keV. The chi-squared value is 1.72 (df = 322).

This basic model skeleton includes a modification for Galactic absorption using the PHABS component, or the dimming of X-ray flux from our object by photoelectric absorption in hydrogen gas in the Milky Way (Reynolds 2003). The column density of hydrogen⁸ toward Ark 120 is $0.098 * 10^{22}$ atoms / cm², according to the low Galactic latitude ($b = -21^\circ$) of Ark 120 in our sky. The basic model also includes a multiplicative modification to the power law to account for instrumental differences. These cross-normalization constants are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Cross Normalization Constants

Instrument	Cross-Normalization Constant
Suzaku / XIS-FI	0.994 ⁹
Suzaku / HXD-PIN	1.180 ¹⁰
XMM / EPIC-pn	0.860 ¹¹

⁸ <http://heasarc.nasa.gov/cgi-bin/Tools/w3nh/w3nh.pl>

⁹ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/suzaku/analysis/abc/>

¹⁰ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/suzaku/analysis/abc/>

¹¹ M. Nowalk, private communication

Section 3.1.2: Fitting a Blackbody Spectrum to the Soft Excess

The power law does not account for the smooth soft excess systematically observed in the spectra of Seyfert galaxies and which is particularly prominent for Ark 120. Due to modeling degeneracies, the soft excess can oftentimes be parameterized sufficiently well with a variety of model components, e.g. soft Comptonization, broken power-law, thermal blackbody, and relativistic reflection (Patrick et al. 2011, Crummy et al. 2006, Arnaud et al. 1985). We found that it is well accounted for by a blackbody component ZBBODY with disc temperature ~ 0.14 keV. Consistent with our phenomenological approach, we added the blackbody component to our basic model, fitting it in the energy ranges over which the soft excess dominates (< 2 keV). Figure 9 shows the data to model ratio plot obtained after this fit. The soft excess is accounted for, leaving a remaining iron line feature and hard excess.

Figure 9 – The Suzaku XIS0+XIS3 (black) and PIN (red) and XMM (green) spectra of Ark 120 plotted alongside data to model ratio plots after fitting < 2.0 keV range with a blackbody component. In contrast to figure 8, this plot shows that the smooth excess has been reasonably accounted for, leaving now a prominent iron line feature around 6 keV and a hard excess beyond 10 keV. The chi-squared is 4.33 (df = 415).

Section 3.1.3: Fitting the Compton Hump and Iron Edge

The hard excess is well accounted for by a PEXRAV modeling component. This component addresses the power law spectrum reflected off of neutral material distant from the black hole (Magdziarz & Zdziarski 1995, MNRAS, 273, 837). It assumes a disk geometry for the neutral material, although in reality the material could be a torus.

Two aspects of this step of modeling are noteworthy. First, we tied PEXRAV normalization (measure of the strength of a model component) to the normalization of the power law, so that the PEXRAV component is consistent with the power law that produces it. Second, we noted

that the PEXRAV reflection scaling parameter determines the strength of the reflector in the PEXRAV component (refer to Table 2 for its final fitted value and error bar).

Figure 10 - The Suzaku XIS0+XIS3 (black) and PIN (red) and XMM (green) spectra of Ark 120 plotted alongside data to model ratio plots after fitting the Compton hump with a PEXRAV component. We see that the hard excess has been accounted for, leaving only a prominent iron line feature around 6 keV. The chi-squared value is 2.67 (df = 449).

Section 3.1.4: Fitting the Broad Iron Line

A variety of model components (DISKLINE, LAOR, RELLINE¹²) exist to model line emission at 6 keV (neutral iron) arising from a relativistic accretion disk. The convolution versions of these model components (RDBLUR, KDBLUR, RELCONV¹³, respectively) apply relativistic and Doppler effects to a spectrum. Whereas RDBLUR assumes a non-rotating black hole and KDBLUR assumes a maximally rotating black hole, the RELLINE / RELCONV model components have a BH spin parameter that can vary freely.

Even though the LAOR and DISKLINE models take into account many of the same parameters as the RELLINE model, the freely varying spin parameter in RELLINE is crucial to our goal of constraining BH spin. To make use of this analytical advantage of RELLINE, we modeled the iron $K\alpha$ line emission with a RELLINE component in our phenomenological model. This model component includes parameters for an emissivity index and for the inclination of the accretion disk. We allowed our spin parameter to vary freely between 0 – 0.998, ruling out a retrograde black hole based on previous work on Ark 120 (Nardini et al. 2011, Patrick et al. 2011).

In addition to the RELLINE disk line emission component, we added a PEXRIV model component (convolved with RELCONV for relativistic smearing of the spectrum), which

¹² <http://www.sternwarte.uni-erlangen.de/~dauser/research/relline/>

¹³ Dauser et al. 2010

simulates an ionized accretion disk. To ensure modeling consistency, we tied together all of the RELLINE and RELCONV parameters. All of the parameters of PEXRIV are the same as that of PEXRAV, except for the free ionization parameter in PEXRIV. Figure 6 shows the model plotted against the data after the aforementioned additions.

Figure 11 - The Suzaku XIS0+XIS3 (black) and PIN (red) and XMM (green) spectra of Ark 120 plotted alongside data to model ratio plots after fitting the broad iron line. We see that the fit is much better than in Figure 8. The chi-squared value is 1.82747 (df = 600).

Section 3.1.5: Refining the Phenomenological Fit with Additional Narrow Iron Lines

In addition to the broadened iron $K\alpha$ fluorescent iron line, other semi-salient iron features exist between 6.40 – 6.97 keV (Basko 1978). In the final part of the phenomenological modeling, we refined the model by using three Gaussian components to address three narrow iron lines that result from the reflection of iron atoms off of matter far from the center of the black hole. These are intrinsically narrow lines unaffected by relativity, so we fixed the widths of these lines at 0.01 keV. The lines that we added are consistent with K-shell emission from neutral iron (6.4 keV), helium-like iron (6.67 keV), and hydrogenic iron (6.97 keV).

Our final phenomenological model is composed of a power law, a blackbody, a PEXRAV and two narrow Gaussians (distant reflector), and a RELLINE for the broad iron line in addition to PEXRIV convolved with RELCONV (blurred reflector). Figure 12 displays the best-fit phenomenological model, with a reduced chi-squared of 1.06 (df = 589). Table 2 displays the best-fit parameters and associated $1-\sigma$ errors for the phenomenological model.

The spin constraint (with $1-\sigma$ error obtained in XSPEC) is 0.71 ± 0.25 .

Figure 12 - The Suzaku XIS0+XIS3 (black) and PIN (red) and XMM (green) spectra of Ark 120 plotted alongside data to model ratio plots for the best-fit phenomenological model. The chi-squared value is 1.06 (df = 589).

Table 2 – Best-Fit Phenomenological Model Parameters

Parameter	Suzaku	1- σ Error	XMM	1- σ Error
6.4 keV Gaussian strength ¹⁴	1.00×10^{-8}	4.47×10^{-6}	1.29×10^{-5}	3.58×10^{-6}
6.67 keV Gaussian strength	6.18×10^{-6}	2.19×10^{-6}	9.02×10^{-6}	3.05×10^{-6}
6.97 keV Gaussian strength	1.948×10^{-5}	2.12×10^{-6}	3.12×10^{-5}	3.92×10^{-6}
RELLINE (blurred) emissivity ¹⁵	1.714	0.21	4.34	2.81
RELLINE strength	5.02×10^{-5}	8.24×10^{-6}	2.45×10^{-5}	2.19×10^{-5}
PEXRIV (distant) ionization ¹⁶	1.10×10^{-11}	-1.00	242.16	165.28
PEXRIV reflection scaling factor ¹⁷	-0.49	0.12	-1.56	0.28
Power law photon index	2.08	1.07×10^{-2}	2.21	1.13×10^{-2}
Power law strength ¹⁸	1.29×10^{-2}	1.17×10^{-4}	2.04×10^{-2}	1.71×10^{-4}
Distant reflector Fe abundance ¹⁹	0.27	0.10	0.27	0.10
Blackbody temperature (keV)	0.13	3.37×10^{-3}	0.13	3.37×10^{-3}
Blackbody strength ²⁰	1.52×10^{-4}	7.90×10^{-6}	1.52×10^{-4}	7.90×10^{-6}
Spin	0.71	0.25	0.71	0.25

¹⁴ units of strength (normalization): total photons $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in the line

¹⁵ power law dependence of emissivity (scales as $R^{-\text{index}}$)

¹⁶ units of ionization: erg cm/s

¹⁷ 0, no reflected component $< rel_{\text{refl}} < 1$ for isotropic source above disk

¹⁸ units of power law normalization: photons $\text{keV}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 1 keV

¹⁹ iron abundance is a fraction relative to solar value

²⁰ $\frac{L_{39}}{[D_{10}(1+z)]^2}$, where L_{39} is the source luminosity in units of 10^{39} ergs $^{-1}$, D_{10} is the distance to the source in units of 10 kpc

Figure 13 – The phenomenological model is comprised of a blackbody (magenta), PEXRAV and two narrow Gaussians for the distant reflector (purple), power law (red), RELLINE + PEXRIV for the blurred reflector (cyan).

Section 3.2 Physical Model

After completing the phenomenological modeling, we fit our data with a physical model that is more physically self-consistent than the component-by-component phenomenological model. Like the phenomenological model, our physical model includes an underlying power law, three Gaussian components for the narrow iron lines, a distant reflector, and a blurred reflector convolved with relativistic smearing.

Instead of PEXRAV for the distant reflector, the physical model employs the local model component REFLIONX²¹ (Ross & Fabian 2005) to represent the disk reflection spectrum. This model assumes that the same physical process causes the soft excess, the iron line feature, and the hard excess, making it more internally self-consistent than a phenomenological buildup. Instead of PEXRIV for the blurred reflector, the physical model employs REFLIONX convolved with RELCONV for relativistic smearing.

Figure 7 displays the best-fit physical model, with a chi-squared of 1.37 (df = 596). Table 3 displays the best-fit parameters and associated 90% confidence intervals for the physical model. The confidence intervals are calculated from an MCMC algorithm, which start with the best-fit parameters and randomly deviate from those values to map out parameter space.

²¹ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/xanadu/xspec/models/reflion.html>

Figure 14 - The Suzaku XIS0+XIS3 (black) and PIN (red) and XMM (green) spectra of Ark 120 plotted alongside data to model ratio plots in the final physical fit. The chi-squared value is 1.37 (df = 589).

Table 3 – Best-Fit Physical Model

Parameter	Suzaku 90% CI	Error	XMM 90% CI	Error
6.4 keV Gaussian strength ²²	(5.67 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 9.52 x 10 ⁻⁶)	(-1.91 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 1.93 x 10 ⁻⁶)	(1.14 x 10 ⁻⁵ , 1.72 x 10 ⁻⁵)	(-3.02 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 2.70 x 10 ⁻⁶)
6.67 keV Gaussian strength	(5.95 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 1.17 x 10 ⁻⁵)	(-3.60 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 2.22 x 10 ⁻⁶)	(2.98 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 1.08 x 10 ⁻⁵)	(-3.65 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 4.19 x 10 ⁻⁶)
6.97 keV Gaussian strength	(0, 3.25 x 10 ⁻⁶)	(0, 3.25 x 10 ⁻⁶)	(4.09 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 1.18 x 10 ⁻⁵)	(-3.45 x 10 ⁻⁶ , 4.33 x 10 ⁻⁶)
RELCONV emissivity ²³	(6.72, 9.70)	(-0.88, 2.09)	(4.79, 5.46)	(-0.39, 0.27)
Blurred reflector ionization ²⁴	(222.18, 269.96)	(-17.74, 30.03)	(276.04, 317.70)	(-19.77, 21.88)
Blurred reflector strength	(4.58 x 10 ⁻⁷ , 6.29 x 10 ⁻⁷)	(-8.60 x 10 ⁻⁸ , 8.47 x 10 ⁻⁸)	(5.67 x 10 ⁻⁷ , 6.53 x 10 ⁻⁷)	(-4.32 x 10 ⁻⁸ , 4.28 x 10 ⁻⁸)
Distant reflector strength	(1.83 x 10 ⁻⁴ , 2.28 x 10 ⁻⁴)	(-1.73 x 10 ⁻⁵ , 2.82 x 10 ⁻⁵)	(2.30 x 10 ⁻⁴ , 2.71 x 10 ⁻⁴)	(-1.52 x 10 ⁻⁵ , 2.52 x 10 ⁻⁵)
Power law photon index	(2.08, 2.10)	(-0.01, 0.02)	(2.06, 2.07)	(-0.01, 0.01)
Power law strength ²⁵	(1.12 x 10 ⁻² , 1.19 x 10 ⁻²)	(-3.31 x 10 ⁻⁴ , 2.92 x 10 ⁻⁴)	(1.60 x 10 ⁻² , 1.66 x 10 ⁻²)	(-3.28 x 10 ⁻⁴ , 3.57 x 10 ⁻⁴)
Distant Fe abundance ²⁶	(0.85, 0.93)	(-0.05, 0.03)	(0.85, 0.93)	(-0.05, 0.03)
Spin	(0.93, 0.95)	(-0.01, 0.01)	(0.93, 0.95)	(-0.01, 0.01)

Section 3.2.1: MCMC Error Analysis

In order to obtain more robust errors, we performed an Monte Carlo Markov Chain simulation. We ran four 10,000-element MCMC chains, starting at random points in parameter space. The covariance matrix that we used consisted of the squares of 1- σ errors produced for each parameter in XSPEC. We burned the first 10% of chains, and then used all four chains to calculate 90% confidence intervals for each parameter in our physical model.

²² units of strength (normalization): total photons cm⁻²s⁻¹ in the line

²³ power law dependence of emissivity (scales as $R^{-\text{index}}$)

²⁴ units of ionization: erg cm/s

²⁵ units of power law normalization: photons keV⁻¹cm⁻²s⁻¹ at 1 keV

²⁶ iron abundance is a fraction relative to solar value

Figure 15 – This figure displays the model components of the best-fit physical model: the REFLIONX (neutral) in purple, the REFLIONX (ionized) in cyan, and a power law component in red. In the soft energy ranges, the reflection associated with the inner disk dominates the reflection associated with the distant reflector.

Figure 16 – This is a probability distribution of our spin parameter calculated using the MCMC chains. This is a reasonable approximation of a gaussian distribution, and the error is 0.01.

Spin is potentially degenerate with other parameters in the fit, such as iron abundance and the emissivity of the accretion disk – we explored this through our MCMC chains and found that these parameter pairs are in fact independently constrained.

Figure 17 – This is a contour plot of the iron abundance and spin parameters, produced using the MCMC chains.

Figure 18 – This is a contour plot of the spin parameter and the emissivity index of the inner disk for *Suzaku* data, produced using the MCMC chains.

Section 4: Discussion

The BH spin constrained in the physical model $0.94^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$ is consistent with the constraints obtained for previous research on Ark 120; it is slightly lower than the value obtained by Patrick et al. 2011 (>0.97) and slightly higher than the provisional value obtained by Nardini et al. 2011 of “ $0.24 < a < 0.93$ at a 99 per cent confidence level, with a best estimate of $a \approx 0.74$.” These differences make sense in light of our different approaches; we employed a more physical approach than Nardini et al, with values of ionization and inclination that fall between the values obtained by both authors.

The chi-squared value (1.37) of the physical fit is not as desirable as the chi-squared value (1.05) of the phenomenological fit, as a chi-squared closer to one indicates a better data to model fit. This results from the different assumptions of the two models. The phenomenological model assumes no reflection in the soft excess ranges, whereas the physical model assumes that all three excess components arise from the reflection of the power law continuum off of ionized and non-ionized material. It is reasonable to infer that the REFLIONX of the physical model (in particular, of the ionized reflector) does not fit the soft excess as well as the blackbody model component of the phenomenological model.

The difference in the goodness of the models may not be as great as the difference in chi-squared values would suggest. This is because the data in the soft energy ranges (< 2 keV) have especially high signal-to-noise ratio, due to the joint analysis of *Suzaku* and *XMM* data. As a result, the two models are especially sensitive to the fit of the model in the soft energy ranges. Any impotence in fitting the soft excess energy range will be magnified in the chi-squared fit; for example, the sharp lines from the distant REFLIONX (Figure 15) may not fit the soft excess as well as the smooth ZBBODY (Figure 13). Nonetheless, we prefer the physical model because it is more physically self-consistent. The consistency in our phenomenological and physical models in both yielding high spin parameters is reassuring, as is their agreement with the spin constraints of Patrick et al. 2011 and Nardini et al. 2011.

A comparison of the model components in Figure 13 (phenomenological fit) and Figure 15 (physical fit) reveal that the blurred reflector is stronger than the distant reflector in the physical model, whereas the normalizations of the two reflectors are more similar in the phenomenological model. In particular, in the soft energy range of the physical model, the blurred reflector model component dominates the distant reflector, suggesting that the parameters associated with the blurred reflector (such as ionization of the accretion disk) may strongly influence the constraint of the spin parameter. The spin constraint we obtained may as a result have been particularly sensitive to the decrease in ionization (276.04, 317.70) from the *XMM* observation in 2003 to (222.18, 269.96) the *Suzaku* observation in 2007.

Section 5: Conclusion

In this paper, we jointly analyzed the bare Seyfert 1 galaxy Ark 120 using *Suzaku* and *XMM* data, to take advantage of a higher signal-to-noise ratio with the combined data. To fit the soft excess, hard excess, and iron $K\alpha$ excess, we employed a phenomenological approach to inform ourselves of appropriate starting parameter values for our physical model, which assumes that all

three excess features result from reflection of the underlying power law continuum. We allowed the BH spin parameter to vary freely within both models, obtaining a constraint of 0.71 ± 0.25 (phenomenological) and $0.94^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$ (physical). We performed a careful MCMC error analysis to obtain robust errors for our physical model. Our spin constraint is consistent with values obtained for previous research obtained by Patrick et al. 2011 (>0.97) and Nardini et al. 2011 ($0.24 < a < 0.93$). Further research is desired to probe the physical nature of the soft excess. Clarification of its physical origin would enable more precise constraint of BH spin.

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